

A STUDY ON COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract:

The present study has been conducted to find out the Communication skills of School teachers at the Higher Secondary level. Further, significant differences between sex, School locality, Residence, Medium of instruction, teaching Experience. A sample of 582 School teachers were randomly selected from two Various Schools, Cuddalore District, Tamilnadu. The fact is that apart from the basic necessities, one needs to be equipped with habits for good communication skills, as this is what will make them a happy and successful social being. In order to develop these habits, one needs to first acknowledge the fact that they need to improve communication skills from time to time. They need to take stock of the way they interact and the direction in which their work and personal relations are going. The only constant in life is change, and the more one accepts one's strengths and works towards dealing with their shortcomings, especially in the area of communication skills, the better will be their interactions and the more their social popularity.

Key Words: Communication Skills & Higher Secondary School Teachers

Introduction:

Education is a process and acts also as an instrument to bring out the innate behavior of the individual. The destiny of a nation lies in its classrooms. The strength of our nation depends on the teacher's ability to rear well-educated, responsible, well adjusted youth who will step forward when the adult generation passes on to retirement. It is the responsibility of teachers, society and government to see that they are physically, mentally, emotionally and educationally healthy. Traditionally teaching has been regarded as one of the four professions along with the practice of law, theology and medicine. The present status of teaching as a profession has come through the ups and down of history. In ancient India teaching had the status of a great profession and it continued up to the middle ages. The teacher was entirely a man of the people and he could claim certain privileges from the community. A real teacher is one who sacrifices his life for his students. He teaches them as he teaches his own children. Besides imparting knowledge to the students, he makes them aware of virtues like love, compassion, self-control, unselfishness, truth and purity in thought, word and deed. A teacher has an important role in molding and shaping the personality of the student. Such a teacher can be described as a 'maker of new age'. He can love and inspire the students and make his profession noble.

Definitions of the Terms Used:

Communication Skills:

Communication has many meanings that are simple and complex. G. T. Hunt (1987) referred to it as "the process of people sending and receiving information." He conceptualized the communication model as involving a speaker, speech, listeners, and feedback.

The ability to communicate is the primary factor that distinguishes human beings from animals. And it is the ability to communicate well that distinguishes one individual from another. The fact, is that apart from the basic necessities, one needs to be equipped with habits for good communication skills, as this is what will make them a happy and successful social being.

In order to develop these habits, one needs to first acknowledge the fact that they need to improve communication skills from time to time. They need to take stock of the way they interact and the direction in which their work and personal relations are going. The only constant in life is change, and the more one accepts one's strengths and works towards dealing with their shortcomings, especially in the area of communication skills, the better will be their interactions and the more their social popularity.

The dominating question that comes here is: How to improve communication skills? Well, the answer is simple. One can find plenty of literature on this. There are also experts, who conduct workshops and seminars based on communication skills of men and women. In fact, a large number of companies are bringing in trainers to regularly conduct sessions on the subject, in order to help their work force maintain better interpersonal work relations.

Higher Secondary School Teachers:

A school having classes up to Standard XII is called higher secondary school. Teachers who are teaching classes up to standard XII are called higher secondary school teachers.

Significance of the Study:

The art of communication involves listening and speaking as well as reading and writing. Teachers need to be highly skilled in all these areas to excel in their profession. Proficient communicators receive information, understand and synthesize it and express themselves at a high level. They make excellent teachers because they are able to transmit knowledge, skills and values. Communication skill is one of the important components of progress of an individual as well as the nation in many aspects. Communication skills is one of the vital factors should be considered because new technology simplifies the workload of the human being. So, findings of the present study will yield fruitful results to the society. Therefore, the present study has high need and importance.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of the present study are:

- ✓ To study the communication skills of the school teachers.
- ✓ To study if there is any significant difference in communication skills between the male and female teachers.
- ✓ To study if there is any significant difference in communication skills between the teachers working in the school located in the urban area and in the rural area.
- ✓ To study if there is any significant difference in communication skills between the teachers residing in the urban area and in the rural area.
- ✓ To study if there is any significant difference in communication skills between the teachers whose medium of instruction was in English and in Tamil.
- ✓ To study if there is any significant difference in communication skills between the teachers having teaching experience up to 10 years and above 10 years.

Method Used in the Study:

Normative survey method is used in the present study.

Sample:

Among the Higher Secondary School Teachers of Cuddalore Districts, 582 teachers were selected as sample for the study.

Tool:

Communication Skills Scale (CSS) to be constructed and validated by the investigator.

Statistical Techniques Used in the Study:

The following statistical techniques have been used in the study:

- ✓ Descriptive Analysis – Mean and SD
- ✓ Differential Analysis- “t”- test only.

Table 1: The Mean and the Standard Deviation of the Communication Skills Scores of the Entire Samples and Its Sub-Samples

S.No	Samples	Sub-Samples	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	“t” Value	Significant at 0.05 Level
1	Entire Sample		582	111.5997	18.3211		-
2	Sex	Male Teachers	121	113.9008	18.8955	1.51*	Not Significant
		Female Teachers	461	110.9957	18.1400		
3	School locality	Rural Area	387	108.2016	16.6862	6.19**	Significant
		Urban Area	195	118.3436	19.5582		
4	Residence	Rural Area	448	110.1094	18.1911	3.65**	Significant
		Urban Area	134	116.5821	17.9348		
5	Medium of instruction	Tamil Medium	162	109.3210	16.6977	1.97*	Not Significant
		English Medium	420	112.4786	18.8554		
6	Teaching Experience	Upto 10 Years	321	113.5171	19.0496	2.84**	Significant
		Above 10 Years	261	109.2414	17.1268		

* Which means Not Significant at 0.05 Level / ** which means Significant at 0.05 Level

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ The communication skills of the school teachers are high.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in communication skills between the male and female teachers.
- ✓ There is a significant difference in communication skills between the teachers working in the school located in the urban area and in the rural area.
- ✓ There is a significant difference in communication skills between the teachers residing in the urban area and in the rural area.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in communication skills between the teachers whose medium of instruction was in English and in Tamil.
- ✓ There is a significant difference in communication skills between the teachers having teaching experience up to 10 years and above 10 years.

Conclusion:

The study revealed that the majority of the higher secondary school teachers selected as samples are having high level of communication skills. So it can be revealed from the investigation that the higher secondary school teachers should develop their communication skills in a constructive way.

In terms of the need for teacher training regarding adopting a teaching style that contribute to the development of communication skills, interview participants showed that more practice is needed in this situation. Thus, they proposed activities such as: participation in specialized courses, practice in schools on the subject, and applications in summer schools. Through the specific school subjects, through content or features for their teaching-learning activity as a communicational situation, teachers made an inventory of a variety of communication skills developed at students using verbal and non verbal skills.

References:

1. Best, John. W, (1963), "Research in Education", Prentice hall of India (p.t) Ltd, New Delhi.
2. Chiș, V. (2005) –Pedagogia contemporană – pedagogia pentru competențe, Editura Casa Cărții de Știință, Cluj-Napoca.
3. Evertson, Weinstein (2011) – Handbook of classroom management, Routledge, New York.
4. Garrett, H.E., (1973), "Statistics in psychology and education", Vakils, Feffer and Simons Ltd., Bombay.
5. Jonnaert Ph., Ettayebi M., Defise R. (2010) - Curriculum și competențe: un cadru operațional; trad. din fr. Iulia Mateiu Cluj-Napoca: Editura ASCR.
6. Muste, D. (2012), Stimularea motivației la elevi prin intermediul unui program educațional specific, Ed. Presa Universitară Clujeană, Cluj-Napoca.